

DOCTORAL RESEARCH ON TRANSLATED FICTION IN 21ST-CENTURY ROMANIA: A METACRITICAL APPROACH

Daniela HAISAN, Associate Professor, PhD
(“Stefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, Romania)

danielahaisan@litere.usv.ro

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5533-1064>

Received: June 1, 2025 | Reviewed: June 4, 2025 | Accepted: June 5, 2025

UDC 81 | DOI from Zenodo

By looking at 46 PhD dissertations defended in Romanian universities in the 21st century, I aim to offer a glimpse of doctoral research on fiction in translation and the ways in which it reflects the current trends in translation (theory) in general. To this end, I adopt a metacritical approach (based on various Translation Studies taxonomies) which highlights regularities and trends in doctoral research in the field of Translation Studies.